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Exploring the relationship between premenstrual dysphoric disorder and disordered eating: a qualitative study

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ABSTRACT

Background: Premenstrual dysphoric disorder (PMDD) causes debilitating psychological and physical symptoms during the luteal phase of the menstrual cycle. Previous research has shown a strong association between PMDD and disordered eating; however, there is limited research from the UK on the impact that PMDD has on eating behaviours. This information is needed to inform appropriate interventions and support. This study aimed to explore the eating behaviours of people living with PMDD in the UK, their experiences of seeking support, and considerations for future interventions.

Method: Qualitative semi structured interviews were conducted with 13 people with PMDD living in the UK. The participants were recruited via an online PMDD support page. The interviews were audio-recorded, transcribed verbatim and thematically analysed.

Results: Six themes emerged: 'dual personality' life with PMDD; the struggle for appropriate PMDD management; the destructive impact of life with PMDD; eating behaviours during a PMDD episode; 'aftermath' (the impact of disordered eating); and accessing support for PMDD-related eating behaviours. Participants described PMDD as severe and distressing, impacting every aspect of their lives. Obtaining an accurate diagnosis and management were challenging, involving dismissive encounters with health professionals, misdiagnoses, and inappropriate treatment. Their eating behaviours fluctuated during different menstrual phases, showing disordered patterns consistent with binge eating disorder, bulimia nervosa, and anorexia nervosa. Many 'managed' their eating habits with harmful strategies such as purging and 'fad diets'. Participants reported both psychological and physical health impacts of their eating behaviour. Few participants sought eating support, and those who did found minimal improvement. Barriers to seeking help included previous 'dismissive' attitudes and a lack of PMDD knowledge among health professionals. Participants recommended PMDD-specific

training for health professionals, specialised eating disorder services, increased information dissemination, and flexible management options.

Conclusion: People with PMDD display disordered eating consistent with eating disorders such as binge eating disorder, bulimia nervosa, and anorexia nervosa. This highlights the need for a greater understanding of the potential shared mechanisms of eating disorders and PMDD. Given that the majority of people with eating disorders are women and individuals assigned female at birth, understanding the relationship with PMDD is integral to shaping appropriate interventions and eating support strategies.

INTRODUCTION

Premenstrual dysphoric disorder (PMDD) is a severe hormone-based mood disorder that significantly impacts an individual's day-to-day activities.^{1,2} PMDD affects 3-8% (average 1 in 20) of people who menstruate worldwide.³⁻⁶ PMDD is characterised by the presence of psychological, physical and somatic symptoms during the luteal phase of the menstrual cycle. It is categorised as a mental disorder by the Diagnostic and Statistical Manual of Mental Disorders (DSM-V)^{7,8} (diagnostic criteria are presented in Table 1) and by the International Classification of Diseases (ICD-11).⁹ Symptoms typically include marked changes in mood, anxiety, depression, irritability and rage, difficulties in concentrating and suicidality. Approximately 74% of individuals with PMDD experience suicidal thoughts, 34% attempt suicide, and 51% self-harm.¹⁰ Symptoms are alleviated at the onset of menstruation, creating a cyclical pattern of symptoms throughout the reproductive years. PMDD symptoms are therefore associated with a significant impact on work, education, social activities, and relationships; for example, PMDD is attributable to approximately 14,492,465 disability-adjusted life years (DALYs).¹¹⁻¹³

Despite this high prevalence and burden, there is still a low level of awareness and understanding of PMDD, both in the general society and the medical community. Data from the International Association of Premenstrual Disorders (IAPMD) suggests that up to 90% of people with PMDD are being misdiagnosed.^{14,15}

Existing quantitative data show a strong association between disordered eating and PMDD, particularly bulimia nervosa and binge eating disorder.^{13,16,17} Nobles et al. 2016 reported that people with PMDD were seven times more likely to have bulimia nervosa than people without PMDD.¹⁷ Eating disorders and their associated consequences are identified by the WHO as one of the major groups of public health problems facing today's generation, with approximately 90% of those diagnosed being females.^{18,19} In the UK, eating disorders affect between 1.25 and 3.5 million people, and the NHS estimates that approximately 6.4% of the UK's adult population show signs of an ED.²⁰ The consequences of disordered eating on the

health of the affected individuals are enumerated with reports showing that between 6-20% of those with eating disorders will die as a result of their disease.^{18,21} Eating disorders are also associated with a financial burden. In the UK alone, costs for managing eating disorders amounted to £8.8 billion in 2019 and £9.4 billion in 2020, with many people experiencing loss of income and paying high prices for treatment.²²

Given the impact of eating disorders and the increased risk of eating disorders in those with PMDD, it is important to develop best strategies of prevention and support for this population.^{16,17,23} There is still a paucity of studies in the UK that explore how PMDD impacts the eating behaviours of people with this condition, the perceived impact this has on their lives and health, and what types of support they need. These questions and answers are key to developing appropriate and sustainable management strategies and highlight the need for qualitative research to explore these research questions and to generate important data to inform tailored interventions.

The aim of this study was to explore the eating behaviours of people with PMDD in the UK.

Four research questions were addressed:

- What are the eating behaviours of people with PMDD?
- What strategies do people with PMDD use to manage their eating behaviours?
- What impact does disordered eating have on the health of people with PMDD?
- What are the experiences of seeking support for disordered eating by people living with PMDD?

Table 1: Diagnostic criteria for PMDD according to the DSM-V

<p>Timing of symptoms</p> <p>A. In the majority of menstrual cycles, at least 5 symptoms must be present in the final week before the onset of menses, start to improve within a few days after the onset of menses, and become minimal or absent in the week post menses.</p>
<p>Symptoms</p> <p>B. One or more of the following symptoms must be present: 1) Marked affective lability (e.g., mood swings, feeling suddenly sad or tearful, or increased sensitivity to rejection) 2) Marked irritability or anger or increased interpersonal conflicts 3) Markedly depressed mood, feelings of hopelessness, or self-deprecating thoughts 4) Marked anxiety, tension, and/or feelings of being keyed up or on edge</p> <p>C) One (or more) of the following symptoms must additionally be present to reach a total of 5 symptoms when combined with symptoms from criterion B above 1) Decreased interest in usual activities 2) Subjective difficulty in concentration 3) Lethargy, easy fatigability, or marked lack of energy 4) Marked change in appetite; overeating or specific food cravings 5) Hypersomnia or insomnia 6) A sense of being overwhelmed or out of control 7) Physical symptoms such as breast tenderness or swelling; joint or muscle pain, a sensation of “bloating” or weight gain</p> <p>Note: The symptoms in Criteria A–C must have been met for most menstrual cycles that occurred in the preceding year.</p>
<p>Severity</p> <p>D. The symptoms are associated with clinically significant distress or interference with work, school, usual social activities, or relationships with others.</p>
<p>Rule Out Other Psychiatric Disorders</p> <p>E. The disturbance is not merely an exacerbation of the symptoms of another disorder, such as major depressive disorder, panic disorder, persistent depressive disorder (dysthymia) or a personality disorder (although it may co-occur with any of these disorders).</p>
<p>Confirmation of the disorder</p> <p>F. Criterion A should be confirmed by prospective daily ratings during at least 2 symptomatic cycles (Note: The diagnosis may be made provisionally prior to this confirmation).</p> <p>G. The symptoms are not attributable to the physiological effects of a substance (e.g., drug abuse, medication or other treatment) or another medical condition (e.g., hyperthyroidism).</p>

Adapted from the Diagnostic and Statistical Manual of Mental Health Disorders, 5th edition. Washington D.C.2013⁸

METHODOLOGY

Study design

A qualitative research design was undertaken using semi structured interviews to gather insight from people with lived experiences of PMDD.

Participant recruitment

This study aimed for a sample size of 12-15 participants. In previous qualitative research on PMDD, this has been shown to achieve data saturation.^{24,25} The Eligibility criteria for study participation comprised: English-speaking people living in the UK who reported a clinical diagnosis of PMDD; aged 18+ years; still of reproductive age (premenopausal); and able to provide consent.

Recruitment was conducted through Instagram's PMDD support community, leveraging its widespread engagement and accessibility. A study poster was shared on the Instagram account known as 'Describing PMDD'. The study poster contained a short description and eligibility criteria of the study and was shared multiple times from September to October 2021. A convenience sampling technique was utilised whereby individuals expressed interest via email to the lead researcher. Among the 30 potential participants who contacted the researcher, 26 were eligible after email screening. All 26 eligible participants received a secure REDCap web link with the participant information sheet (PIS) and consent form. After reading the PIS, participants could ask questions before providing informed consent. Of the 26 potential participants, 18 provided consent. Of these 18, 4 did not respond to follow-up communication, one was excluded for not having a doctor's diagnosis, and a final sample of 13 participants was included in the study.

Data collection

The interviews were arranged for agreeable time with the participants. All the interviews were completed online via the Zoom platform (between September 30th and October 28th, 2021). A semi structured interview guide was developed and used for all the interviews (see

supplementary files). The interview questions were piloted with three non-study participants to refine the interview process and questions prior to data collection.

Sociodemographic data and general questions related to participants' lives with PMDD were first covered before various aspects of their PMDD and its influence on their eating behaviours were explored. At the end of the interview, participants had the opportunity to add any additional information they felt was important. The day following each interview, participants received an email to check on their wellbeing and a link to a support resource (National Centre for Eating Disorders <https://eating-disorders.org.uk>).²⁶ All the interviews were conducted consistently by one researcher (REN) and recorded via the Zoom recording facility.

Data analysis

The audio recordings were transcribed verbatim. Any personal or identifiable data said by the participants during the interviews were blanked out. NVivo qualitative software version 12 was used to organise and code the data using Braun and Clarke's²⁷ approach to thematic analysis. This involved three phases of coding and analysis. In Phase 1, initial codes were established by the lead researcher (REN), and to minimise bias and ensure rigour in data analysis, a second researcher (LM) independently performed a phase 1 analysis on six of the 13 transcripts. The codes were discussed by the two researchers. In Phase 2, the codes were refined and sorted into major themes. Both researchers discussed the themes at this stage. In Phase 3, a final round of refining the codes and themes was performed by the lead researcher (REN), who discussed and agreed with both researchers. Sociodemographic data were entered into Microsoft Excel version 2013 and exported to the analysis software R version 4.0.3 for analysis. Continuous variables are reported as means and ranges while discrete variables are reported as frequencies and percentages.

Ethics

Ethical approval was granted by the University of Glasgow's College of Medical, Veterinary, and Life Sciences Ethics Committee. Informed consent was obtained from all participants in the study.

RESULTS

Thirteen participants completed an interview. Twelve (92.3%) identified as female, and one as nonbinary (7.7%). The interview duration ranged from 30-90 minutes, with an average of 52 minutes. Eleven (84.6%) participants identified as Caucasian British, one (7.7%) as Black British and one (7.7%) as German-British. Their ages ranged from 26-43 years, with a mean of 34.31 years (SD = \pm 4.83 years). Four (30.8%) participants had a master's degree, seven (53.8%) had a bachelor's degree, and two (15.4%) had up to secondary school education.

Participants had lived with PMDD symptoms for 5–26 years, averaging 15.95 years (SD = \pm 2.41 years). The time since receiving a doctor's diagnosis ranged from 0.25–14 years, with an average of 2.62 years (SD = \pm 1.56 years). The period between the onset of symptoms and diagnosis ranged from 4–21.5 years, with an average of 13.22 years (SD = \pm 3.29 years). Seven (53.8%) participants were in full- or part-time employment, four (30.8%) had left their jobs due to PMDD, and two (15.4%) were students. Twelve participants provided information on their weight and height, and their BMIs were calculated, ranging from 20.94 kg/m² to 47.27 kg/m² with a mean of 29.33 kg/m² (SD = \pm 6.29 kg/m²). According to the WHO BMI classification²⁸, 5 (41.7%) were categorised as obese (BMI \geq 30 kg/m²), 1 (8.3%) was overweight (BMI \geq 25 kg/m² and \leq 30 kg/m²), and 6 (50%) were normal weight (BMI=18.5-<25 kg/m²).

Thematic analysis produced 97 initial codes, which, upon further analysis, were grouped into six main themes and associated subthemes (see Figure 1). Themes are presented in the text alongside direct quotations identified by the participant's (P) study number.

Figure 1 Themes and subthemes identified

Theme 1. 'Dual Personality': Life with PMDD

Life during a PMDD episode (luteal phase)

Participants described their lives with PMDD as “horrendous”, considering it an “imposter”. They felt split between two identities and endured extreme physical and psychological symptoms for years. These included depression, irritability, anxiety, and suicidality. Resisting suicidal thoughts was described as an “inner battle”. Physical symptoms included severe fatigue, joint pains, and binge-eating. They felt powerless to prevent these events and spent years coping with what they described as incomprehensible emotions. Mood swings were abrupt, leaving them feeling “out of control” and engaging in behaviours such as going to unfamiliar places and continuous crying.

“And usually, it would be that at 11 o'clock in the morning, everything's fine and at 11:05 it's like somebody has turned the lights off, like somebody, uh, flick the switch {...} and all of my sense of ever being able to be happy again, is drained.” (P10)

Most participants found their psychological symptoms excruciatingly painful. At their worst, they felt “disconnected”, suicidal, and like “a bomb exploding inside their heads”. Some resorted to self-deprecating eating habits as a coping mechanism (reported further under Theme 5.4).

“Um, I've also considered so many types of suicide every month. I've written notes to truck drivers, the train drivers to apologise for what I'm about to do when I just don't want to be here. And the only thing that is a kind of comfort is food, but then it's because you use it for self-deprecating purposes.” (P9)

Some participants living with other challenges deemed PMDD to be the most debilitating, fearing that living with PMDD would shorten their lifespans:

“There's nothing else in my life um, that is as disruptive {...} I'm Trans[gender], I'm polyamorous, I'm disabled, I'm neurodiverse, I've got hearing issues {...} I've lived off benefits, um, and have experienced poverty {...} and the one thing that is the most disruptive in my life and compromises my quality of life and makes me worry that I'm not going to live to the age of 35 is PMDD.” (P10)

Life outside of PMDD Episode (non-luteal phases)

Outside of the luteal phase, most participants described feeling “normal”, “controlled”, stable or optimistic. They regained sociability, healthy eating habits, and a sense of happiness and excitement. Although they experienced regret over PMDD-related behaviour, the cessation of suicidal thoughts brought relief:

“I'm just happy, {...} I'm better at work, um, I'm getting tasks completed, I'm more confident, I'm more sociable. I've got my resilience back. Um, I feel like I can take and deal with stuff and be more pragmatic.”(P8)

However, some lived in fear, anticipating the recurrence of symptoms with the next menstrual period:

“I used to be okay, like I would be so happy and productive and hyper and living life in the good part in the good two weeks, but because I'd lived with it for so long, {...} I'd be like, well, I know I'm going to ovulate in five days and then {...} Almost like what's the point in getting stuck into something or trying, because it's all going to be just knocked down in five days' time.”(P13)

Theme 2. The struggle for appropriate PMDD management

The challenge of gaining a diagnosis for PMDD

All participants had negative experiences obtaining a diagnosis. Those who sought help for PMDD were initially misdiagnosed with other mental disorders such as generalised anxiety or depression, while others with physical symptoms were misdiagnosed with rheumatological or immune disorders. Many were sceptical of their diagnoses, as they were aware of a pattern of symptoms with their menstrual cycle. They spoke about how they tracked their symptoms and undertook their own research, initially receiving their diagnoses either online or through family or friends:

“And I knew it wasn't depression because I was fine for two weeks. Um, and it was always coming up to my period {...} and then I started making notes of everything because she [GP] had just told me, um, to take antidepressants {...} I started writing notes and I realised it was in the 10 to 16 days leading up to my period. So, I started Googling about, um, PMS and, and extreme forms of that and that's when I found PMDD.”(P2)

Participants stated how, even when they were certain about the possibility of a PMDD diagnosis, their requests for help went unheard. They described this experience as being “constantly dismissed” by general practitioners (GPs) or being assured that their mood fluctuations were merely part of a “normal” female experience. In some cases, participants were told that “people reacted differently to situations and some humans are just unable to cope with life”, which left them feeling upset, helpless and suicidal.

“There have been many, many times over the years um, I'm really being told that everyone has stress in their lives and at one time I got told, you know, um, some people can cope with life and some people can't. Uh, and, and, and that was it and I felt suicidal at that point. Um, and that was very upsetting.”(P5)

Faced with misdiagnoses and dismissive reactions, some participants turned to private healthcare. They documented in detail their frustrations and mistreatment from health professionals:

“I was diagnosed privately, um, because I got so desperate. Um, I, I went and asked so many times at my GP. Please, can you help me please? {...} And they just said, no, it's just PMS or no, you're too young. And then eventually it got to the point where I was so desperate that I wrote down a letter of everything that they said to me, {...} how it affects my life, how I've lost every single job {...} Um, I asked to speak to Nick Panay's [a consultant gynaecologist known for specialising in PMDD] team, um, because I wasn't messing around anymore.” (P13)

Lack of adequate treatment for PMDD

After the struggle to obtain an accurate diagnosis, participants then faced inadequate treatment and support. Despite trying various options, none of the treatments offered effectively managed their PMDD. GPs dismissed requests for specific therapies, leading some to reluctantly try psychiatric or hormonal prescriptions they knew would not work for them. Those who did try pharmacological suggestions found the medications unhelpful, often causing debilitating side effects:

“They [GPs] throw things at you like contraceptives when they don't even know what they're going to do to you and they convince you, and I've been, um, on contraceptives probably about four times in my life to try and help with PMDD and all of them have made me worse because I'm intolerant to progesterone. So it's just like they've handed me a bomb and just made me worse.” (P9)

Participants indicated their dissatisfaction with the medical community, citing a lack of understanding and research on PMDD as important contributors to their poor management. Dissatisfaction drove many of them to try many alternative therapies. Some even argued that PMDD management was not considered important, as it did not directly affect men:

“Um, you're left trying to find some snake merchant type remedies that people recommend on the internet. And, um, it makes you feel like there's nothing that's ever going to help and that makes it harder {...} There's a real let down from the medical community, um, in terms of {...} taking people seriously that this is their experience and then offering some kind of

help. Um, and there isn't enough research out there and I'd guarantee it'd be different if men were struggling with it.” (P10)

Theme 3. The destructive impact of life with PMDD

Living in fear (of the next cycle) and guilt

Participants expressed living in constant fear and guilt, dreading the monthly recurrence of their experiences and regretting the pain they caused loved ones. This fear and guilt of "failing" consumed them, feeling like a burden to their families and constantly seeking to make amends.

“I've been so disgusting, really, really so disgusting to my husband. Absolutely verbal disgusting, and that's not me, you know, I wouldn't ever want to be spoken that way, but I've spoken to him dreadfully. I always feel very guilty as well because I've got two really beautiful children and I love them very much, and I can see what I have in my life and yet I still want to kill myself.” (P7)

Damage to relationships and social life

Participants reported that the hardest part of them living with PMDD was how their symptoms disrupted their personal relationships and social life. They recalled feeling constantly judged and rejected by those around them. They isolated themselves from their loved ones as a means of protecting others and themselves from harm, often leading to the dissolution of their intimate relationships and established friendships:

“It's the effect that it has on my mum, my partner, and my relationships with my friends and my family {...} I've lost a lot of friends and past romantic relationships because they don't understand. Sometimes I want to stay away not to feel hurt or hurt my partner cause the worst pain is mainly watching him when he can't cope,{...} when I'm in a heap on the floor saying that I don't want to be here anymore and it's horrible.” (P13)

Participants described the debilitating impact of PMDD on their education and careers. They struggled to complete their education, faced recurrent absenteeism and were unable to meet

workplace obligations. They frequently terminated employment, with some abandoning their careers because they were unable to cope:

“I’m not working anymore. I’ve just had to quit working and left my career. I always felt like a lunatic and just couldn’t cope. Um, it’s uh, yeah, I’ve kind of had to give up my work throughout my life because of it.” (P6)

Theme 4. Eating behaviours during a PMDD episode

‘Out of Control’: Patterns of bingeing and starvation

All participants reported eating behaviours in line with disordered eating, eight of whom had a current or prior diagnosis of an eating disorder.

Many participants described their relationship with food as unhealthy, marked by intense cravings for various food types, especially sugary, starchy, fatty, salty, and sour foods, or combinations thereof. These cravings intensified near the onset of menstruation:

“In the next few days that I’ll start to menstruate, it’s like craving, so, and it can be really weird stuff. So I like last month, what was it? Uh, cheese, onion and gherkins {...} [It] tends to be salt, sugar, or vinegar.” (P6)

Most participants reported having a marked increase in appetite, especially during their worst PMDD episodes, which led to binge eating. They reported losing their sense of satiety and eating “rubbish” or “crappy” foods in an “out-of-control” manner until they felt uncomfortably full. Participants said that they lost their ability to make appropriate food choices despite knowing it would help manage their PMDD symptoms. They noted how their eating and PMDD interacted; when their PMDD felt “out of control”, their eating got “out of control” and vice versa:

“In PMDD mode, I don’t even know what I’m doing. I just get out of control; I’ll just pick up loads and loads of loads and loads of food. I don’t think about it. It just happens {...} I just keep eating. And I noticed that not only my PMDD affects my eating, but my eating affects my PMDD massively. Um, like if my PMDD was slightly stable and I ate uncontrollably, my PMDD becomes out of control as well.” (P3)

Some participants binged for comfort due to extreme psychological symptoms, whereas others did so for self-punishment, feeling that they “deserved it” for having PMDD. They felt angry if unable to satisfy cravings, despite feeling horrible and frustrated shortly after eating, with that frustration fuelling them to consume more:

“I will go looking for cake. I crave sugar. Um, I will get angry if I can't get cake. You can't fight all the battles at once. So, I just think, give me all the Maltesers, get me through the next half an hour. It's like a, it's like a self-deprecating punishment that you do to yourself. And you think you feel rubbish anyway. So, you deserve to feel more rubbish {...} and you think I might as well eat more. And then you feel sad, feel sick, or just be disgusted with yourself.” (P9)

Although many participants reported binge eating, some experienced starvation due to impaired cognition on their worst PMDD days. When feeling overpowered by severe symptoms, they prioritised “surviving” rather than eating:

“Um, I don't tend to eat at all if I'm, if I'm really struggling, {...} sometimes I'll wake up at six and won't eat until like 5:00 PM because I just can't be bothered. I just concentrate on surviving.” (P4)

Participants reported that the hardest part of managing their eating was having to repeat the same cycle monthly, alongside managing the anger they felt if they could not satisfy their cravings or if anyone tried to prevent them from bingeing:

“Um, um, the anger and repeating the cycle every month is the hardest bit {...} I get quite angry and, you know, and scream and, um, I'm not allowed to drive so my husband will often get sent out to go and get cakes and crisps and everything that he can find or think of. And then of course, he'll, yell at me and say, you're really gonna do this again after you tell me every month, uh, you wish you didn't do that, and I get even more angry.” (P11)

Immediate Coping Strategies

Participants described using coping strategies that focused mainly on healthier eating or preventing weight gain. They also described how the strategies most often

failed to help them regulate their eating. Both positive and negative strategies were reported.

▪ **Positive strategies**

Meal planning: Most participants reported trying to plan meals ahead of time. This included buying healthy foods or creating large nutritious meals and freezing them for later use. Some participants reported that meal planning was quite helpful:

“I’ll try and cook a lot of nutritious food in one go and put it in the freezer for later, but not often, but when I do it, it was quite helpful.”(P1)

Getting help: Most participants received help from family, friends, or housemates with meal preparations or prompts, alleviating the burden of deciding what to make and ensuring that they had a nutritious meal or felt cared for:

“My partner or a friend who also has PMDD would frequently check to be sure I have eaten. Having somebody check in with me or say, how are you doing then you saying, oh, this is the worst PMDD episode in 10 months and oh, and they send you like dinner. So you don’t have to worry about that. I think those are the most helpful things I’ve got.” (P10)

In contrast, other participants avoided asking for help. They feared they would be unable to control their desires to eat and would become defensive if stopped, causing a rift with their loved ones:

“My partner, um, he tries, but doesn’t always say things in the right way. So, I try not to ask [for help], because I don’t want to cause problems, um, between us. Um, and because of my relationship around food, if I ask somebody, please, can you not let me not eat that or anything, then I’d probably get nasty {...} if they said something in that moment like oh no, that’s not good for your PMDD or you sure you should be eating that? I would just, I wouldn’t be able to take it.” (P3)

Avoiding socialising or shopping: Participants avoided social events or eating out to prevent feelings of anxiety and shame about their inability to manage their eating. They also

avoided food shopping to prevent them from being overwhelmed and unable to control their urge to buy junk food.

“Um, socially, it's bad, I avoid going out Um out for meals, just makes me feel anxious and like the amount of time I've gone, like, uh, like with my parents, it's hit and miss. We've had to abandon meals in restaurants. It's been really embarrassing.” (P8)

Distraction: Many participants used distraction techniques to prevent them from eating, typically with activities that involve using their hands.

“Um, I do try have a bath or read a book which occupies your hands, you know, something like that, instead, cos you can't possibly eat while in the bath.” (P5)

Participants expressed that the above strategies were not always helpful. They were unable to adhere to them due to their irresistible food cravings. They referred to PMDD using words such as ‘the beast’ or ‘her’:

“It depends who's in charge and I have to see them as two separate entities um, and the very nature of the beast is that it's very powerful. Um, if I can beat her, I'll be successful, but it will be hard all day. Um, but if, if she wins, I just let it win because, I can't be bothered to fight her anymore. So, they [coping strategies] can be successful, and they can't be, I'd say, uh, probably 60/40 in her favour.” (P9)

- **Negative strategies**

Fad diets: Several participants had tried one or more fad diets, all of which had been futile:

“Uh, the amount of fad diets I've done. I've done everything, you know, Slimming World, Weight Watchers, uh Five-Two diets, uh cabbage soup, uh, Slim Fast milkshakes, all these kinds of things. I'm like they don't work.” (P2)

Purging: Many participants expressed that they were either using laxatives or making themselves sick after food binges:

“To be honest with you, after bingeing weirdly I still do make myself sick or take laxatives {...} This is really awful, and I would feel really ashamed and disgusted with myself, just really guilty.” (P11)

Some mentioned a history of eating disorders, which they linked to the onset of PMDD:

“A few years ago, after like bingeing, and then I would be really unhappy with my body, and I started to use laxatives {...} I think this was around the time of my PMDD onset.” (P6)

No strategy: Some participants reported having no strategies to manage their eating during their PMDD episode. They described how they felt “paralysed” by their mental health at the time:

“I just cannot think, my mental health gets so bad that I just focus on surviving, and I do not try any strategy and food is not even a consideration at such point.” (P7)

Theme 5. ‘Aftermath’: The impact of disordered eating

Strategies for recovery and repair

As described above, the majority of participants had engaged in strategies – albeit typically unsuccessful - to manage their eating *during* a PMDD episode. They also employed different strategies for recovery and repair *following* a PMDD episode.

Food tracking: Food tracking was among the most used strategies. Some participants reported using phone tracking apps or mentally tracking food before consumption. However, most of them found tracking stressful and obsessive, prompting them to discontinue.

“Like I will weigh everything, make sure everything's tracked in my tracker and it got to a point where it was too much {...} because it did become a bit obsessive.” (P4)

Food restriction: The majority of participants reported using food restriction for several years or having used it in the past as a perceived means to counteract their bingeing and manage their weight:

"I would be very restrictive with food and, um, weigh myself every day. Um, yeah, there was a time it was really unhealthy." (P12)

'Overly Healthy' Meals: Some participants responded by eating what they considered 'extremely healthy meals' made of fruits and vegetables only:

"When I'm feeling strong and eating healthy, I eat extreme healthy. I would eat solely fruits and vegetables. {...} I kind of try to do some pre-damage control and then PMDD hits and it's all the damage and then I do post-damage control again."(P5)

Over exercise: Over exercising was another strategy that several participants had used. They described their realisation that this approach was unhealthy and exhausting, leading them to cease:

"I've done all kinds of intensive weight reduction exercises, um practically everything you could think of, and it ended up just too uncomfortable, very unhealthy and tiring." (P2)

Re-strategising: Participants spoke about how their strategies both during and after their PMDD episodes were typically unsuccessful.

"I have done over the last, how many years? Um, pretty much all of that. I've over exercised, uh, at home gym. Uh, I was counting calories. Um, I I've had, uh bulimia and stuff like restriction restricting as well. Uh, I had taken, um, laxative, like tablets and things like that, but like fat burning things and have discovered that none worked." (P3)

After failed coping strategies, some participants reverted to either a vegan diet, a "typical" healthy lifestyle, or intuitive eating where they accepted that 'poor' eating was a part of their PMDD and did not identify any food as good or bad. They found these strategies beneficial:

"I have accepted that I cannot always eat right, and I do not beat myself up for whatever reason. Uh, I had experienced an ED before, and I know how frustrating it could be. So, I have now resulted to intuitive eating, and I do not recognise any food as good or bad and I eat anything." (P10)

Reflecting on the Impact of Disordered Eating

Participants reported several physical and psychological health impacts, alongside other social-related impacts. Physically, participants reported weight gain, being overweight, or unhealthy weight loss.

“I definitely have weight gain because my weight fluctuates so severely when my PMDD is like under control and when it's not under control.” (P2)

They also reported frequent migraines, stomach irritation, the fear of developing new health conditions and the exacerbation of underlying conditions:

“I believe due to my restrictive or starving habits, I do get like frequent stomach irritations and migraines, and it also like really aggravates my IBS [Irritable Bowel Syndrome]. I also have gall bladder problems which definitely feels worse after um, when I eat poorly.” (P8)

Psychologically, most participants expressed feelings of guilt, humiliation, or embarrassment toward themselves as a result of either failing to maintain ideal eating habits or retaliating against loved ones, who advised them:

“It's kind of like the shame. {...} Um, because you know that you failed with your eating and you know you're just going to do it again even though you say that you won't {...} You also feel so much guilt from how you had shut up your husband who tried to advise you to eat healthy {...}” (P9)

They also reported feelings of being judged and shamed by others:

“My husband would say if you eat that you'll feel rubbish um, and people will come and like family members especially will say like, oh, you eat a lot. Don't you? And that gets me really angry, defensive and feeling very low of myself especially as I am a big girl, like I'm clinically overweight.” (P2)

They also described how PMDD impacts their self-esteem and body image:

“PMDD makes you have a really, really low opinion of yourself {...} I'm not happy with my body image. I'm convinced I've put on 10 stone. I'm you

know, it, it kind of plays havoc with the way that you feel about yourself and your confidence.” (P13)

Theme 6. Accessing support for PMDD-related eating behaviours

Support sought

Although participants who identified as having eating problems wished for external support, most of them had not yet sought any support. Of those who had, they had sought help for eating disorders or being overweight after suffering for extensive time periods. Participants typically attributed their ED to the onset of their PMDD. They reported having sought either professional support or support from online groups. Regarding professional support, most had undergone general therapy sessions for eating disorders or body coaching programmes for weight loss. Those who sought help for eating disorders reported mixed results, while those who underwent body coaching programs for weight loss reported some successes, which were, however, not sustainable due to the inconsistency of living with PMDD:

“When I was in Uni years ago, um, I think years into my PMDD, my eating disorder was really bad, and I went to my, uh, senior support officer and they, uh, got me psychotherapist, uh, and that definitely did help.” (P3)

Participants also reported having sought help from online support groups. Although they found this beneficial when it was a PMDD-specific group, they described general ED support groups as overwhelming:

“I find that there's people on Instagram who talk about PMDD, um, lots of stuff around sugar-free and hormone balancing with food. I find that really helpful.” (P5)

“I was part of the eating disorder one, but that was too much. It made me worse because I {...} got overwhelmed with so much information.” (P3)

Barriers to seeking support

Participants identified four key reasons for the delay in seeking help for their eating behaviours. First and most importantly was the perceived dismissive attitudes of health professionals and their lack of knowledge on PMDD.

“I don't want to be let down as I was before having my diagnosis. I don't want to put myself through all of that and then still be in the exact same position or worse because you feel slapped, or you feel neglected.” (P12)

Secondly, participants reported fear of the cost of therapy:

“I don't know how much it costs to see someone, but {...} you got to pay for it and I might not afford for it.” (P1)

Thirdly, they feared feeling embarrassed and judged:

“Embarrassment, mainly, um, just, the fear of being judged {...} or like, oh, you're just making excuses because you're fat.” (P9)

Lastly, some participants felt that they were burden enough to their families and could not ask for more support from them:

*“The thought that my partner already does enough to help me {...}, so if he had to also help with my eating habits, it can just be too much for him.”
(P12)*

What support is needed?

Participants identified the following sources of support as important for managing PMDD-related eating behaviours.

Information: All participants identified the need for PMDD and eating awareness to be disseminated via various sources, including research, the government, workplaces, and school curricula. Emphasising the need for information, participants lamented how they wished they had the knowledge that their eating was related to their menstrual cycle and how this may have saved them years of frustration and suffering:

“Just knowing that cravings were a sign of PMDD would break that cycle of eating habits altogether {...} and then bingeing, and that must have been luteal, and the restricting was follicular. So, I was restricting, bingeing, restricting, and then each time it, both sides were just getting stronger and stronger {...} I had no idea that there was even a cycle to my ED.” (P3)

Training health professionals and providing specialised eating disorder services:

Participants emphasised the need for specialised PMDD health professionals and digital services such as online support groups, apps and websites that address PMDD and eating problems:

“We need specialist dieticians or Um, like PMDD specialist nurses with like nutritional training {...} that is geared towards people with a menstrual cycle {...}” (P5)

Better and flexible management options: Participants cited the importance of further research for effective treatment and desired more autonomy in their treatment decisions:

“Um, what I would need is for someone to fund actual, like medical research into why people have PMDD and what helps it? And, um, then for whatever treatment has been found to be successful {...}, have options that one can autonomously choose and not following this routine that does not work.” (P10)

Eating-friendly workplaces: Participants noted the need for comfortable working places with nutritious meals for staff and facilities such as microwaves to promote healthy eating:

“So, I work in a massive hospital, but we lack menstrual-friendly and nutritious desserts for staff and oh, {...} I don't always have a microwave, so I can't always heat up food. So, then my options are really limited as what I can eat at work.” (P2)

Expectations and Goals for Future Self

When thinking of the future, participants wished for better and more consistent eating habits. Most wished for better methods to manage their eating, for weight loss, and for living without guilt:

“That {...} I don't make myself feel as guilty as I do for days and um, that I try not to make myself sick, {...} and I lose some weight and be able to move about more.” (P2)

DISCUSSION

The overall aim of this research was to explore the eating behaviours of people living with PMDD in the UK. The findings are discussed below in relation to the specific research questions.

General experiences of people living with PMDD in the UK

Consistent with the current literature^{4,11,12,25,29,30}, our findings emphasised the profound psychological and physical impact that people with PMDD experience, as well as its detrimental effect on their quality of life.

Participants in our study, like those in Osborn *et al*²⁵, faced challenges ‘being heard’ by health professionals, leading to rejection and misdiagnoses, often for 10+ years before a correct diagnosis of PMDD. People with PMDD are commonly misdiagnosed with psychological disorders^{25,31}, highlighting the difficulty faced by health professionals in differentiating PMDD from other psychiatric disorders. The recommended pharmacotherapies^{29,32–34} (often antidepressants or hormone therapies) were only marginally beneficial to our participants, with some reporting aggravation of their symptoms. This is similar to the case reported by Dahlgren & Qvigstad.³⁵

Participants felt ‘dismissed’ by health professionals who often made them feel that they had exaggerated their symptoms. This may reflect broader gender biases in healthcare. Recent evidence suggests a significant gender disparity in treatment, with women's experiences often being disregarded.³⁶ This gap widens further when women present with reproductive concerns, particularly related to menstruation.^{37,38} Furthermore, the perceived dismissive attitudes towards PMDD could be linked to its psychiatric presentation. Data show that psychiatric conditions are often stigmatised in healthcare settings, leading to the disregard and rejection of patients by professionals.^{39,40}

Our findings support previous research^{3,11,12}, demonstrating that PMDD frequently results in suicidal ideation, suicide attempts, inability to maintain healthy interpersonal relationships, and

inability to perform key daily activities such as work and parenting roles. In our study, PMDD resulted in 31% (n=4 of 13) of participants being unable to work, while others lost productivity after having to take time off work.

Eating behaviours of people with PMDD in the UK

Participants typically experienced heightened appetite and intense cravings for high-sweet, high-fat-sweet, and high-salt or sour foods during PMDD episodes. In line with previous studies^{17,35,41,42}, uncontrolled eating and binge eating were the most frequently reported eating behaviours. These eating behaviours were described as “self-punishment” methods or coping mechanisms in an attempt to counteract the intense psychological symptoms experienced during PMDD episodes, notably depressive symptoms. According to research, depression alone strongly contributes to uncontrolled eating in those with PMDD.^{41,43,44} Some participants in our study described periods of unconscious starvation that resulted from the severe cognitive symptoms they were experiencing. This is a novel finding from our study that warrants further investigation.

Our participants highlighted the mutual impact of PMDD and eating behaviours. They highlighted that when their PMDD fell out of control, their eating got out of control and vice versa. This finding supports recommendations^{1,14,34} for a focused approach to managing PMDD-related eating issues as part of holistic PMDD management alongside pharmacological treatment.

Strategies utilised by people with PMDD in the UK to manage their eating behaviours

Our study revealed positive coping strategies during and after the luteal phase, previously unexplored in the PMDD literature. The strategies included meal planning, distraction techniques, getting help, food tracking, and avoiding socialising or shopping. While NHS²⁰ and NIMH¹⁸ endorse these strategies to mitigate impulsive and binge eating in the general population, our participants reported minimal success, possibly because, unlike in the general

population, those with PMDD experience impulsive and binge eating alongside increased hunger and a marked appetite.^{41,42} Success may also be limited by the repetitive cyclical nature of PMDD, which participants described as “exhausting”. This highlights that people with PMDD may require focused approaches to managing their eating problems.

One participant, who adopted an intuitive eating strategy, reported better outcomes. Intuitive eating, the main aspect of cognitive behavioural therapy (CBT), has been proven effective in treating eating disorders in the context of mental disorders such as depression and anxiety.^{44,45} Given that PMDD is characterised by debilitating psychological symptoms, future research should further explore this treatment option in PMDD subjects with disordered eating.

We also identified negative coping strategies, both during and after the luteal phase. Luteal-phase strategies included fad diets, purging with laxatives or induced vomiting. These actions are consistent with the eating disorder bulimia nervosa and support previous research on PMDD’s association with bulimia nervosa.^{17,35,46,47} Nobles et al. 2016¹⁷ reported that people with PMDD had up to 7 times higher odds of having bulimia nervosa than did those without PMDD. Nonluteal-phase strategies included food restriction, over exercising and dieting. These actions align with the eating disorder anorexia nervosa.⁷ Traits of anorexia nervosa have not been identified before in studies of people with PMDD. Although these findings are novel, higher rates of anorexia nervosa have been identified in people with bipolar disorder, and people with comorbid anorexia nervosa and bipolar disorder are significantly more likely to be female: OR=6.25 (95% CI=2.9--13.44, $p<.01$, N=4).^{48,49} Given that bipolar disorder is a common misdiagnosis for PMDD and that PMDD commonly coexists with bipolar disorder, undetected bipolar disorder could potentially mediate the elevated rates of eating disorders among people with PMDD.^{50,51}

Health impacts of the eating behaviours of people with PMDD in the UK

Weight gain, migraines, gastric irritation, and exacerbation of existing chronic conditions were the main physical health impacts cited by our participants. Their mean BMI was 29.33 kg/m² (range 20.94--47.27 kg/m²), with 50% of our sample categorised as overweight or obese. This

prevalence is higher than the estimated prevalence of 29% obesity among UK females;⁵² but similar to that reported in other studies of people with binge eating.^{53,54} However, high BMI values may not always reflect actual obesity as BMI does not distinguish between lean muscle and body fat. For instance bodybuilders and athletes often have high BMI values but low body fat mass.^{55,56}

Consistent with the literature^{57,58}, our participants reported feelings of guilt, shame and low self-esteem as major psychological impacts of their eating habits. These emotions could stem from individuals perceiving themselves as “failures” due of their perceived inability to maintain healthy eating habits.^{59,60} Additionally, studies have shown that many women are conditioned to place significant importance on their body shape and weight when assessing their own self-worth.^{59,60} As many of our participants were overweight or obese, this may have influenced their perception of their body shape leading to feelings of shame and low self-esteem.

Experiences of seeking eating support by people living with PMDD in the UK

To our knowledge, the experience of seeking eating support by those with PMDD has not been explored in other studies. In this study, most participants had not sought any eating support, and the few who did sought professional or online help from eating support groups either to manage their disordered eating and/or to manage weight gain. The experiences were mixed. Professional therapies had minimal and unsustainable benefits, whereas online support from PMDD-specific support groups was beneficial. Advice from general eating support groups was viewed as unhelpful, as people found this overwhelming with too much information. This highlights the need for tailored eating support for PMDD, considering its unique challenges and symptoms.

The main barriers to seeking eating support were previous negative experiences of seeking PMDD support from health professionals, cost, and fear of becoming a family burden. Health professionals’ knowledge and behaviours towards patients are well-recognised as major determinants of seeking support for mental health.^{61–63} Feeling dismissed and judged results in feelings of rejection and embarrassment and reduces the possibility of seeking help in the

future.⁶¹⁻⁶³ Additionally, a lack of understanding among health professionals creates doubt and feelings of dread, which discourages individuals from seeking help.^{61,64}

Our participants expressed their desire to eat better and more consistently in the future and identified various needs to support themselves and others with PMDD, including improved dissemination of information, training of health professionals, and research for better treatment.

Disseminating information via schools, workplaces, the medical community and websites was highlighted as essential. PMDD often starts in adolescence, a high-risk period for eating disorders, with reports⁶⁵ suggesting that 30% of adolescents exhibit behaviours indicative of eating disorders. Therefore, educating adolescents on PMDD and eating problems could prompt early recognition and intervention. Furthermore, PMDD is strongly associated with self-harm and suicidality.^{30,32} We suggest that adding PMDD awareness to school curricula, as demonstrated by NICE's guidelines on self-harm and suicide, is crucial.⁶⁶ Similarly, raising awareness in workplaces could lead to more accommodating environments for those with PMDD, as seen in cases of perimenopausal workplace awareness.⁶⁵ Online awareness campaigns, NHS-affiliated websites, and PMDD support groups were suggested as avenues for disseminating accurate information and providing support for those with PMDD-related eating disorders. Raising awareness within the medical community and training health personnel, particularly dietitians, are crucial for the early diagnosis and proper management of PMDD and its associated eating problems. Effective treatment of PMDD symptoms, including disordered eating, requires comprehensive management, as evidenced by cases where symptoms are alleviated only after multiple treatments.^{29,35,67} Further research is needed to develop more effective treatments for managing PMDD and associated eating problems, considering options beyond surgery for those who are unable or unwilling to undergo such procedures. The findings of this study align with the research priorities identified by the UK's stakeholder informed research agenda.⁶⁸

Strengths and limitations

Our findings provide in-depth insights into the eating behaviours of individuals with PMDD, their barriers to accessing support and recommendations to overcome these barriers.

A limitation of this study is that our participants were predominantly White British individuals living in England. As healthcare in the UK is devolved, accessing treatment may vary across and within nations; therefore the generalisability of our findings to the wider population may be limited. Future studies may consider the use of a PMDD screening tool to provide clinical confirmation of PMDD, as the current study relied on participants' affirmations of receiving a doctor's diagnosis.

Conclusion

Our findings demonstrate that people with PMDD living in the UK face significant challenges in obtaining a proper diagnosis and treatment for their condition, and they exhibit disordered eating in line with binge eating disorder, bulimia nervosa and anorexia nervosa. Given that 1 in 20 women/AFAB have PMDD and that the majority of people with EDs are women/AFAB, the relationship between these disorders is crucial to understand further. Our findings highlight ongoing gaps for future research and will help inform two pathways of best practices: (1) to support professionals in the management of people with PMDD and disordered eating and (2) to support professionals in the management of people with EDs who may have undiagnosed PMDD.

Declarations

Abbreviations

DALY: Disability Adjusted Life Year(s)

ED: eating disorder(s)

PMDD: Premenstrual Dysphoric Disorder

Ethics approval and consent to participate

Ethical approval was provided by the Medical, Veterinary and Life Sciences Ethics Committee of the University of Glasgow (reference number: 200200130). Informed consent was obtained from all participants.

Consent for publication

Not applicable.

Availability of data and materials

All data generated or analysed during this study are included in this published article and its supplementary information files.

Competing Interests

I declare that the authors have no competing interests as defined by BMC, or other interests that might be perceived to influence the results and/or discussion reported in this paper.

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Authors' contributions

REN was lead researcher for the study and undertook recruitment, data collection, data analysis and preparation of the manuscript. LM was supervisor of the study and contributed to all aspects of the research including review and approval of the final manuscript. JR piloted the qualitative interviews and contributed to preparation of and approval of the final manuscript.

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